

Consumer Preferences for Purchasing Local Fruits at The Farmers Market Supermarket in Palembang City

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ABSTRACT: Fruit consumption in Palembang City remains below the World Health Organization (WHO) recommendation and has not reached an optimal level. Meanwhile, the increasing availability of imported fruits creates competition and affects consumer preferences toward local fruits. This study aims to identify the attributes influencing consumer preferences, analyze the dominance of physical and non-physical attributes, and examine the effect of imported fruit presence. A quantitative survey was conducted involving 100 respondents selected through accidental sampling. Data were analyzed using the Fishbein multi-attribute model, multiple linear regression, and path analysis. The results show that freshness, taste, and price are the main attributes shaping consumer attitudes. The attitude score (Ao) is categorized as high (101.167 or 67.44%), indicating that stronger positive attitudes are associated with higher consumer preferences for local fruits. Regression analysis reveals that product attributes significantly influence preferences, with physical attributes as the dominant factor. Meanwhile, the presence of imported fruits does not have a significant effect. These findings indicate that consumer preferences are mainly driven by product attributes and attitudes, suggesting that improving the quality of local fruits is essential to enhance their competitiveness.

KEYWORDS: Consumer, Local Fruit, Preference, Purchase, Supermarket.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia, as a tropical country, has highly favorable environmental conditions for the growth of diverse horticultural crops, particularly fruits ¹. This enables continuous production of local fruits, which play an important role not only in meeting domestic consumption needs but also as high-value economic commodities ². Local fruits, cultivated and adapted to local environmental conditions, contribute significantly to food security, nutrition, and the livelihoods of local farmers ³. Despite this potential, the availability of local fruits does not always align with consumption levels. In Palembang, fruit production fluctuated between 2018 and 2022.

Table 1. Fruit Production and Consumption in Palembang City (2018 – 2022)

No.	Year	Production (Quintals)	Consumption (Kg/Capita/Week)
1.	2018	310.627	0.979
2.	2019	436.914	0.564
3.	2020	781.507	0.682
4.	2021	535.761	0.645
5.	2022	435.807	0.732

Source : Statistics Indonesia (BPS), 2023

Table 1 shows that fruit production in Palembang City fluctuated during the 2018–2022 period, with the highest production recorded in 2020, followed by a decline in subsequent years. In contrast, fruit consumption remained relatively low and did not consistently follow production trends. This indicates a mismatch between the availability of local fruits and consumption levels, suggesting that factors beyond supply, such as consumer preferences, play a crucial role in purchasing decisions⁴. Consumer preferences are shaped through the evaluation of both intrinsic attributes (e.g., taste, freshness, color) and extrinsic attributes (e.g., price, brand, food safety, and origin)⁵. While local fruits generally offer advantages such as freshness and affordability⁶, many consumers still prefer imported

fruits due to perceived superior quality, uniformity, and premium image⁷. The increasing volume of fruit imports in recent years further reflects strong market demand for imported products.

Table 2. Fruit Import Volume in Indonesia (2020 – 2024)

No.	Year	Import Volume (Tons)
1.	2020	638.556
2.	2021	775.422
3.	2022	749.855
4.	2023	689.924
5.	2024	780.576

Source : Statistics Indonesia (BPS), 2023

Table 2 further illustrates the trend of fruit import volumes in Indonesia from 2020 to 2024. The data show that import volumes remain relatively high and fluctuate over time, with a notable increase in 2021 and 2024. This pattern reinforces the indication of strong and sustained market demand for imported fruits. The consistent presence of imported fruits in the market may intensify competition with local products and influence consumer preferences, particularly as imported fruits are often perceived to offer superior quality, uniformity, and a more premium image. In modern retail settings, such as Farmers Market Supermarket in Palembang, local and imported fruits are displayed side by side, allowing consumers to directly compare product attributes. This comparison process can influence consumer perceptions, attitudes, and ultimately their preferences. Therefore, this study aims to analyze consumer preferences toward local fruit purchases and examine the influence of product attributes and the presence of imported fruits as a comparative factor.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and setting

This study was conducted at Farmers Market Supermarket located in Palembang City, South Sumatra Province, Indonesia. The research site was purposively selected because Farmers Market is part of the modern retail network of PT Supra Boga Lestari Tbk, which operates numerous outlets across Indonesia and specializes in fresh products, including fruits. At this location, local and imported fruits are displayed side by side with well-maintained quality, allowing consumers to directly compare product attributes. This condition is considered appropriate for analyzing consumer preferences toward local fruits in a modern retail setting. Data collection was conducted between October and December 2025.

Participants, samples, or data sources

The population consisted of all consumers present at Farmers Market Palembang. The sampling technique used was accidental sampling, where respondents were selected based on their availability and willingness to participate during the data collection process, provided they met the research criteria (Sugiyono, 2019). The criteria for respondents were consumers who were actively shopping at the supermarket. A total of 100 respondents were selected, which is considered adequate for statistical analysis and sufficient to represent the population characteristics (Hair et al., 2014). The data used in this study consisted of primary and secondary data. Primary data included consumer preferences toward product attributes such as color, taste, freshness, price, promotion, and availability, as well as respondent characteristics including age, occupation, and purchase frequency. Secondary data were obtained from Statistics Indonesia (BPS), as well as from scientific journals, books, and other relevant sources.

Data collection and measurement procedures

Primary data were collected using structured questionnaires based on a 5-point Likert scale. To meet the assumptions of parametric analysis, ordinal data were transformed into interval data using the Method of Successive Intervals (MSI). This method converts cumulative proportions into standardized scores based on a normal distribution, as introduced by Thurstone and further explained by Guilford (1954). Data collection was carried out through direct visits to the research location three times per week and was supported by brief interviews to ensure data accuracy and relevance. Data quality was assessed through validity and reliability tests. Validity was determined based on correlation coefficients ($r > r\text{-table}$ or $\text{Sig.} < 0.05$), while reliability was evaluated using

Cronbach's Alpha with a threshold greater than 0.60 (Ghozali, 2018). Prior to further analysis, classical assumption tests including normality, multicollinearity, and heteroskedasticity were conducted to ensure the suitability of the regression model (Gujarati & Porter, 2009).

Statistical or analytical methods

The data were analyzed using both descriptive and quantitative approaches. Descriptive analysis was applied to summarize respondent characteristics and to provide an overview of consumer preference patterns. To address the first research objective, the Fishbein multi-attribute model was used to evaluate consumer attitudes toward local fruit attributes (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975), formulated as:

$$A_o = \sum (b_i \times e_i)$$

Where:

A_o = attitude

b_i = belief

e_i = evaluation

Consumer attitude levels were classified into five categories, namely very low (6–34.8), low (34.9–63.6), moderate (63.7–92.4), high (92.5–121.2), and very high (121.3–150), based on equal interval classification. This classification was developed by dividing the range of possible scores into equal intervals, allowing for a clearer interpretation of the overall attitude level of consumers toward local fruit attributes.

To address the second research objective, multiple linear regression analysis was employed to examine the influence of physical attributes (X_1) and non-physical attributes (X_2) on consumer preferences (Y), in order to determine the extent to which each variable contributes to shaping consumer decision-making. This analysis allows for identifying both the direction and magnitude of the relationships between independent variables and the dependent variable, expressed as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Where:

Y = consumer preferences

X_1 = physical attributes

X_2 = non-physical attributes

β_0 = constant

β_1, β_2 = regression coefficients

e = error term

Furthermore, to address the third research objective, path analysis was applied to evaluate both direct and indirect relationships among variables, including the mediating role of consumer attitudes (M), formulated as:

$$M = \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e_1$$

$$Y = \beta_3 X_1 + \beta_4 X_2 + \beta_5 M + e_2$$

Where:

M = consumer attitudes (mediating variable)

Y = consumer preferences

β = path coefficients

e_1, e_2 = error terms

All statistical analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics version 29. The analytical procedures were carried out following standard quantitative statistical practices to ensure the validity and reliability of the results. Prior to conducting the main analyses, data were tested to meet the necessary statistical assumptions, ensuring that the models were appropriate for further interpretation. Each method was applied based on its specific analytical objective, where multiple linear regression analysis was used to examine

the direct effects of independent variables on consumer preferences, while path analysis was utilized to assess both direct and indirect relationships, including the mediating role of consumer attitudes. These analyses were conducted separately using different model specifications to maintain methodological consistency and to avoid overlapping assumptions between analytical approaches. Indirect effects were calculated as the product of path coefficients (e.g., $\beta_1 \times \beta_5$), while total effects were obtained by summing the direct and indirect effects. This approach enables a more comprehensive understanding of the relationships among variables, particularly in identifying both the magnitude and dominance of each variable within the overall analytical model. Furthermore, the use of these complementary analytical techniques provides a more robust interpretation of consumer behavior by capturing both immediate and mediated effects (Kline, 2015).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis was used to summarize and present the basic characteristics of the data, including respondent demographics and purchasing behavior.

Table 3. Respondent Characteristics

No.	Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Gender	Male	38	38%
		Female	62	62%
2.	Age	<20 years	8	8%
		21-30 years	47	47%
		31-40 years	28	28%
		>40	17	17%
3.	Occupation	Entrepreneur	12	12%
		Housewife	27	27%
		Employee	40	40%
		Student (University)	15	15%
		Student (School)	3	3%
		Others	8	8%
4.	Purchase Frequency	Weekly	14	14%
		Every Two Weeks	38	38%
		Once a Month	32	32%
		Rarely	16	16%

Table 3 shows that respondents were predominantly female and largely within the 21–30 age group. Most respondents were employees and exhibited a relatively regular purchasing frequency of local fruits, particularly on a biweekly basis. This pattern indicates that the sample represents active consumers with relatively stable consumption behavior toward local fruits in a modern retail setting.

Product Attribute Analysis Using the Fishbein Multi-Attribute Model

This section analyzes consumer attitudes toward local fruit attributes using the Fishbein multi-attribute model. The analysis aims to identify the relative importance of each attribute by combining consumer beliefs about attribute performance and their evaluation of attribute importance, thereby determining which attributes most strongly influence consumer attitudes toward local fruits.

Table 4. Belief and Evaluation Scores of Local Fruit Attributes

No.	Atributtes	Belief (Bi)	Evaluation (Ei)	Score (Bi x Ei)
1.	Fruits Color	4.05	4.20	17.01
2.	Fruits Taste	4.55	4.20	19.11
3.	Fruits Freshness	4.69	4.61	21.62
4.	Fruits Price	4.27	4.04	17.25
5.	Promotion	3.30	3.45	11.38
6.	Product Availability	3.59	4.12	14.79
Total Ao (Consumer Attitudes)				101.167

Based on Table 4, the Fishbein multi-attribute analysis shows that consumer attitudes toward local fruits at Farmers Market Supermarket in Palembang are determined by the interaction between belief (bi) and evaluation (ei) for each attribute (bi × ei). Freshness records the highest score (21.62), indicating it as the primary determinant of consumer preference, followed by taste (19.11), highlighting its key role in influencing satisfaction. Color (17.01) and price (17.25) also contribute notably, reflecting the importance of visual appeal and economic considerations. Meanwhile, product availability (14.79) has a moderate influence, whereas promotion shows the lowest score (11.38), suggesting a limited role in shaping consumer decisions compared to intrinsic product attributes. The total attitude score (Ao) of 101.167 falls within the high category (92.5–121.2), indicating a strong and positive consumer attitude toward local fruits, which indicates that the higher the level of attitude, the stronger the consumer preference for local fruit, characterized by a good assessment and a greater tendency to choose and buy local fruit. This implies that most attributes are perceived favorably and are important in influencing consumer preference and purchase decisions.

Dominance of Product Attributes (Physical vs. Non-Physical)

This section examines the relative dominance of physical and non-physical product attributes in influencing consumer preferences for local fruits. Multiple linear regression analysis is employed to assess the extent to which each attribute contributes to consumer preferences and to identify the most influential factors in the decision-making process.

Table 5. Classical Assumption Tests

No.	Test	Variable	Indicator	Value
1.	Normality	-	Asymp. Sig (2-tailed)	0.200
2.	Multicollinearity	X1	Tolerance	0.872
		X1	VIF	1.147
		X2	Tolerance	0.872
		X2	VIF	1.147
3.	Heteroskedasticity	X1	Sig.	0.573
		X2	Sig.	0.198

Table 5 presents the results of the classical assumption tests, including normality, multicollinearity, and heteroskedasticity. The normality test shows an Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value of 0.200, which is greater than 0.05, indicating that the data are normally distributed. The multicollinearity test results reveal that all independent variables have tolerance values of 0.872 (> 0.10) and VIF values of 1.147 (< 10), suggesting that there is no multicollinearity problem in the model. Furthermore, the heteroskedasticity test shows significance values of 0.573 for X1 and 0.198 for X2, both exceeding 0.05, indicating the absence of heteroskedasticity. Overall, these results confirm that the regression model satisfies the classical assumptions and is suitable for further analysis.

Table 6. Regression Model Summary and ANOVA Results

No.	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error	F-value	p-value
1.	0.568	0.323	0.309	0.733	23.115	0.000

Table 6 presents the results of the regression model summary and ANOVA test. The R value of 0.568 indicates a moderate relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. The coefficient of determination (R Square) of 0.323 shows that 32.3% of the variation in consumer preferences can be explained by the independent variables included in the model, while the remaining 67.7% is influenced by other factors outside the study. The Adjusted R Square value of 0.309 further confirms the model’s explanatory power after adjusting for the number of variables. Additionally, the F-value of 23.115 with a significance level of 0.000 (< 0.05) indicates that the model is statistically significant, meaning that the independent variables simultaneously have a significant effect on consumer preferences.

Table 7. Partial Regression Results (t-test)

No.	Variable	Coefficient (B)	t-value	p-value
1.	Constant	0.639	1.802	0.075
2.	X1	0.370	4.007	0.000
3.	X2	0.298	2.966	0.004

Table 7 shows the results of the partial test (t-test), indicating that both physical attributes (X₁) and non-physical attributes (X₂) have a significant effect on consumer preferences (Y), as their significance values are below 0.05. Physical attributes show a stronger influence, with a higher t-value (4.007) compared to non-physical attributes (2.966), indicating that observable product characteristics such as freshness, appearance, and color play a dominant role in shaping consumer preferences. Non-physical attributes, including price and product availability, also significantly influence consumer decisions, although to a lesser extent. Meanwhile, the constant is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). These findings suggest that consumers tend to evaluate products in stages, where physical attributes are assessed first, followed by economic and availability considerations, both of which contribute to the final preference for local fruits.

The Effect of Imported Fruit Availability on Consumer Preferences

This section examines the effect of imported fruit availability on consumer preferences for local fruits by incorporating consumer attitudes as a mediating variable. Path analysis is employed to assess both direct and indirect relationships, thereby providing a more comprehensive understanding of how external market conditions influence consumer preferences through internal evaluative mechanisms. It is important to note that the analytical framework and variable specification in this model differ from those applied in the regression analysis, as the path model explicitly accounts for the mediating role of consumer attitudes in capturing indirect effects.

Table 8. Classical Assumption Test Results

No.	Test Type	Model	Variable	Value	Result
1.	Normality	X1, X2 -> M	Residual	Sig = 0.200	Normally Distributed
		X1, X2, M -> Y	Residual	Sig = 0.200	Normally Distributed
2.	Multicollinearity	X1, X2 -> M	X1	Tolerance = 0.961; VIF = 1.040	No Multicollinearity
			X2	Tolerance = 0.961; VIF = 1.040	No Multicollinearity
			X1, X2, M -> Y	X1	Tolerance = 0.855; VIF = 1.169
		X2	Tolerance = 0.862; VIF = 1.160	No Multicollinearity	
		M	Tolerance = 0.771; VIF = 1.297	No Multicollinearity	
		3.	Heteroskedasticity	X1, X2 -> M	X1
X2	Sig = 0.925				No Heteroskedasticity

No.	Test Type	Model	Variable	Value	Result
		X1, X2, M -> Y	X1	Sig = 0.577	No Heteroskedasticity
			X2	Sig = 0.939	No Heteroskedasticity
			M	Sig = 0.483	No Heteroskedasticity

Table 8 shows the results of the classical assumption test results, indicating that all regression models satisfy the classical assumption tests. The normality test shows that residuals are normally distributed (Sig. = 0.200 > 0.05). Multicollinearity is not detected, as all tolerance values are above 0.10 and VIF values are below 10. Additionally, no heteroskedasticity is found since all significance values exceed 0.05. These results confirm that the regression models are statistically reliable and appropriate for further analysis.

Table 9. Coefficient of Determination (R²) Results

No.	Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error
1.	X1, X2 -> M	0.479	0.229	0.212	0.762
2.	X1, X2, M -> Y	0.612	0.375	0.355	0.727

Based on Table 9, the coefficient of determination indicates that the model explains 22.9% of the variance in consumer attitudes (M), suggesting that the presence of imported fruits (X1) and fruit attributes (X2) have a moderate explanatory contribution. In contrast, the second model explains 37.5% of the variance in consumer preferences (Y), indicating an improved model fit when consumer attitudes are included as an additional predictor. The increase in R² highlights the importance of attitudes in strengthening the explanatory power of the model.

Table 10. Simultaneous Significance Test (ANOVA)

No.	Model	Dependent Variable	F-value	p-value
1.	Model 1	Consumer Attitudes (M)	14.403	0.000
2.	Model 2	Consumer Preferences (Y)	19.159	0.000

Based on Table 10, the F-test results show that both models are statistically significant at the 1% level (p = 0.000). In the first model, X1 and X2 jointly influence consumer attitudes (M), while in the second model, X1, X2, and M simultaneously affect consumer preferences (Y). The relatively high F-values (14.403 and 19.159) indicate that the models provide a good overall fit and that the independent variables collectively explain variations in the dependent variables.

Table 11. Partial Significance Test (t-test)

No.	Model	Variable	Coefficient (B)	t-value	p-value
1.	Model 1	Constant		3.057	0.003
		X1	0.315	3.466	0.001
		X2	0.303	3.334	0.001
2.	Model 2	Constant		0.245	0.807
		X1	0.162	1.851	0.067
		X2	0.230	2.642	0.010
		M	0.405	4.405	0.000

Based on Table 11, in the first regression model, both the presence of imported fruits (X1) and fruit attributes (X2) have positive and statistically significant effects on consumer attitudes (p < 0.01), indicating their strong contribution in shaping attitudes. In the second model, fruit attributes (X2) and consumer attitudes (M) significantly influence consumer preferences, while the presence of imported fruits (X1) is not statistically significant (p = 0.067). This suggests that preferences are more directly driven by product-related attributes and are indirectly influenced by imported fruit presence through attitudes.

Table 12. Direct Effects (Path Coefficients)

No.	Variable Relationship	Path Coefficient
1.	X1 -> M	0.315
2.	X2 -> M	0.303
3.	X1 -> M -> Y	0.162
4.	X2 -> M -> Y	0.230
5.	M -> Y	0.405

The path coefficients indicate that both X1 (0.315) and X2 (0.303) positively affect consumer attitudes, with relatively similar magnitudes. However, in influencing consumer preferences, consumer attitudes (M) exhibit the strongest direct effect (0.405), followed by fruit attributes (0.230), while the effect of imported fruit presence (0.162) is comparatively weaker. This pattern suggests that attitudes act as a key determinant in translating attribute perceptions into preference formation. Furthermore, this finding indicates that consumers tend to internalize product-related information through their attitudes before forming final preferences. It also highlights the importance of psychological evaluation processes in strengthening the relationship between product attributes and consumer decision-making.

Table 13. Indirect Effects through Consumer Attitudes

No.	Path	Calculation	Indirect Effect
1.	X1 -> M -> Y	0,315 x 0,405	0.128
2.	X2 -> M -> Y	0,303 x 0,405	0.123

The indirect effect analysis shows that the presence of imported fruits (X1) and fruit attributes (X2) influence consumer preferences through attitudes, with coefficients of 0.128 and 0.123, respectively. The relatively similar values indicate that both variables exert comparable mediated effects. This confirms that consumer attitudes function as an intervening variable that transmits the influence of external and product-related factors to consumer preferences.

Table 14. Total Effects (Direct and Indirect Effects)

No.	Variable	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect
1.	X1 -> Y	0.162	0.128	0.290
2.	X2 -> Y	0.230	0.123	0.353

The total effect results reveal that fruit attributes (X2) have the largest overall impact on consumer preferences (0.353), exceeding the effect of imported fruit presence (X1) at 0.290. This indicates that intrinsic product characteristics play a more dominant role in shaping preferences. The contribution of indirect effects also highlights that part of this influence operates through consumer attitudes, reinforcing the mediating role of attitudes in the overall model.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that consumer preferences for local fruits are primarily determined by intrinsic product attributes, particularly physical characteristics such as freshness and taste. The Fishbein multi-attribute analysis demonstrates that these attributes receive the highest Bi×Ei scores, indicating their dominant role in shaping positive consumer attitudes. The regression results further confirm that physical attributes exert a stronger influence on consumer preferences than non-physical attributes, as reflected by the highest standardized coefficient (β). This suggests that consumers prioritize product quality over external factors such as price, promotion, and availability when making purchasing decisions. Moreover, the path analysis reveals that the presence of imported fruits does not have a statistically significant effect on consumer preferences (β = 0.174; p > 0.05). This indicates that imported fruit availability is not a determining factor in influencing consumer choice. Instead, consumer preferences are largely driven by internal factors, particularly consumer attitudes and evaluations of product attributes.

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